

**The Air Force Logistics Command Fiber Optics Program
A Strategy to Systematically Introduce the Technology**

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Abstract

This paper will describe the management of the Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC) Fiber Optics Program, a subset of the overall Air Force Fiber Optics Program. For overview and perspective, we will begin by outlining the features and benefits of the fiber optics technology. Then, we will discuss the objectives of the Air Force Fiber Optics Program. Next, we will discuss the AFLC program and how it relates to and supports the Air Force program. Finally, the paper will give an overview of AFLC's involvement in Tri-Service and Department of Defense activities.

<i>DIELECTRIC TRANSMISSION MEDIUM</i>	NO SPARK HAZARD AND HIGH VOLTAGE ISOLATION
<i>REDUCED SIZE AND WEIGHT</i>	DECREASED MOBILITY AND MANPOWER REQUIREMENTS
<i>TAP RESISTANT</i>	TEMPEST SECURE

Background

A constant concern in data transmission is sending ever-increasing amounts of information with greater efficiency over a medium requiring less space and weight. As speeds increase and more information is required, the problems of preserving the quality and integrity of a signal in copper cable also increase. Fiber optic technology provides both the capability and the capacity to handle these requirements. Added to these performance features, other inherent features pave the way for reliability and maintainability enhancements to Air Force systems. Among these are electromagnetic interference/radio frequency interference (EMI/RFI) immunity which gives us the benefit of no crosstalk or EMI filters, reduced size and weight which may decrease mobility and manpower requirements, and tap resistance which offers TEMPEST security to communications systems. A summary of the features and benefits are listed in the table below.

The Defense Department has actively pursued fiber optics applications, and has demonstrated fiber optic cables and hardware. Rapidly-changing components and materials forced the DoD to provide an orderly growth vehicle for the technology. The vehicle had to address the critical areas of development, standardization, and support. Responding to this situation, the DOD and the Air Force each embarked upon programs to systematically introduce fiber optics into systems.

Air Force Fiber Optics Program

Created in 1981, the program aims to provide efficient centralized control for the orderly application of fiber optics technology into USAF communications and transmissions systems to meet user needs. Interoperability among fiber optics systems is of paramount concern and can only be accomplished by limiting the proliferation of independently developed non-standard equipments. The program provides the management oversight to coordinate fiber optics developments through the appropriate standards agencies. Finally, the program directs the Air Force to remain abreast of the most current fiber optic technology by establishing necessary ties to commercial industry and ensuring that the Air Force makes the most effective use of the latest state-of-the-art technology.

WHY USE FIBER OPTICS?

FEATURE	BENEFIT
<i>EMI/RFI IMMUNITY</i>	NO CROSSTALK OR EMI FILTERS
<i>LARGE BANDWIDTH</i>	HIGHER DATA RATE EXPANDABILITY
<i>EXTENDED TRANSMISSION RANGE</i>	INCREASED REMOTING CAPABILITY

The program is being managed by three implementing commands--Air Force Systems Command (AFSC), Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC), and Air Force Communications Command (AFCC). AFSC has lead responsibility.

AFLC Fiber Optics Program

Consistent with the Air Force Fiber Optics Program, the AFLC program has two primary objectives. First, it will provide for the orderly application of fiber optics to existing Air Force weapons systems. Second, it will ensure logistics support and technical management for fiber optics items (Federal Supply Group 60). In order to do this, the Command has designated a single program manager to see that this is done.

The AFLC Program Manager (PM) has been directed to exercise the authority and management responsibility to organize, plan, direct, and control the AFLC Fiber Optics Program. The PM is located at Sacramento Air Logistics Center (SM-ALC) and is also in charge of the AFLC Fiber Optics Technology Center (FOTC). The FOTC was established in 1983 with the purpose of giving AFLC the resources to gain the expertise necessary to support the application of fiber optics in Air Force systems. The Technology Center is a 3,500 square foot facility with \$1.5 million in equipment and seven engineers. It is used to support the AFLC System Program Managers (SPMs) and Item Managers (IMs) in solving reliability and maintainability problems.

The PM is also the Fiber Optics Technology Application Program Manager (TAPM). The TAPM initiative is an AFLC effort to better capitalize upon emerging laboratory technologies and use them to solve problems in existing AFLC-managed weapons systems. The TAPM initiative targeted 22 emerging technologies, which included fiber optics, and identified a program manager for each. The initiative also set up the infrastructure along with the management responsibilities to transition the technology into existing weapons systems. The AFLC Fiber Optics PM fulfills the TAPM responsibility by creating a fiber optics technology awareness throughout the Command.

There are four other specific organizations within AFLC which are actively involved with the AFLC Fiber Optics Program. First, Logistics Command Headquarters, specifically HQ AFLC/MMT, has policy and program direction responsibility. Second, the Communications-Electronics and Space Management Division at SM-ALC/MMC has FSG-60 item management responsibility plus they manage many other systems and items which are good candidates for fiber optics insertions. Third, the Air Force Acquisition Logistics Center (AFALC) is AFLC's formal link to the AFSC, the development community. They must provide fiber optics support considerations to systems being developed in AFSC. Fourth, the Aerospace Guidance and Metrology Center (AGMC) is the Air Force organization in charge of all calibration requirements for

fiber optics components and systems. They are setting up the capability to calibrate fiber optics components at Precision Measurement Equipment Laboratories at various Air Force facilities.

Two objectives of the AFLC program are one, to bring the rest of the Command on line to be aware of the fiber optics technology; and two, to establish a strong link between the AFLC program and the research and development community in AFSC. To meet the first objective the FOTC is on a marketing campaign to create a fiber optics technology awareness at all of the AFLC centers. They are doing this through a technology roadshow that is making its way to all the centers during 1988. The FOTC is also setting up a series of video teleconference (VTCN) meetings for technology crosstalks among the centers. Also, the FOTC is advising other centers on equipment, personnel, and training needs for fiber optics. Seed shops for fiber optics proof of concept projects will eventually be set up at all the centers and will be funded out of the FOTC equipment funds. To meet the second objective, AFLC is setting up informal links to AFSC in order to focus development efforts in a direction which will yield effective fielded systems.

DOD Relationships

AFLC is directing fiber optics on a DOD-level by providing the Chairperson for the Joint Commanders Group for Communications-Electronics (JCG-CE) Fiber Optics Management Panel (FOMP). Significant FOMP activities include restructuring FSG-60 to accommodate state of the art components, setting up an interim standards process which is responsive to DOD's needs and will prevent the proliferation of unique components, creating a Tri-Service database to coordinate individual efforts of the services, and establishing interservice requirements contracts.

Summary

The fiber optics technology offers many opportunities in terms of reliability and maintainability enhancements and in terms of performance improvements. Only through a concentrated program can the Air Force capitalize on the technology and bring systems on line which are supportable. The AFLC Fiber Optics program was designed to meet these objectives. Finally, by leading tri-service activities, AFLC is taking the necessary steps to direct the effective application of fiber optics within all of DOD.

Acknowledgements

The features and benefits table is courtesy of the AFLC Fiber Optics Technology Center at Sacramento Air Logistics Center, McClellan Air Force Base, California.

References

1. The Air Force Fiber Optics Program Management Directive, April 7, 1986.
2. The Air Force Logistics Command Fiber Optics Program Action Directive, December 1, 1986.